

Results from the 2024 Digitalization Survey in Materials Science and Engineering

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In 2020, around a year before the start of the NFDI-MatWerk project, we conducted a survey with the aim of gaining insights into the current status of digitalisation in the MSE community, awareness of the FAIR principles and specific needs.

Almost 3 years after the launch of NFDI-MatWerk, we are addressing these issues again with a survey that was conducted online from mid-June to the end of July 2024.

This time, we were able to reach around 150 participants.

With the findings from the survey, we not only want to present the current status, but also actively gain insights into the current needs in the MSE community in order to be able to steer our developments in a targeted manner and meet these needs.

Around 50% of participants are having a PhD degree, 40% have a masters or diploma degree and 10% are professors. Thus, the survey covers the main target groups for NFDI-MatWerk, with more than 50% of all participants belonging to the four subject areas of Mechanical Properties of Metallic Materials and their Microstructural Origins, Computer-Aided Design of Materials and Simulation of Materials Behaviour from Atomic to Microscopic Scale, Metallurgical, Thermal and Thermomechanical Treatment of Materials as well as Synthesis and Properties of Functional Materials.

Also, from all other subject areas within Materials Science and Materials Engineering, referring to the DFG classification, we were able to cover a wide field of participation.

Around 30% of participants have their main employment at the university and 30% at non-university, public research institutes, 10% are from industry and surprisingly, no participants are from universities of applied sciences. More than 50% of the participants are under 39 years old.

Methodically, around half of the participants are experimentalists, around 20% are doing simulation and another 20% are building models (several answers could be selected).

We asked if the **FAIR principles are known and applied**: Around 70% know them and apply them partially, while only 8% apply them fully and more than 13% do not know the principles at all.

About 35% of our participants say that they are already involved in projects that aim for better implementation of the FAIR principles, 24 participants in total are involved in NFDI-MatWerk.

Interestingly, when we asked for **possible or current fields of joint digitalization efforts**, the highest ranking answers were “Share my existing solutions with others and make them available for further development” with 72 answers, “Semantically structure my research data using community standards” with 74 answers and “orientate myself on common community standards for meta and context data structuring” with 72 answers. 66 participants want to “Attend training courses on standardizing solutions and make my knowledge available as a supplement”. But only 36 participants would “make labor capacities available for joint development projects (e.g. from your own group or personally)”.

When we asked for the **most urgent needs**, almost 90% answered “Contextual information: Standardized ways are needed to provide others with to make others understand the full background of the measured and simulated data sets.” “Software interfaces (API): Manufacturers and scientists should jointly define uniform standards for transferring data from the machine to a storage form.” and “GUI compatibility: Software with graphical user interfaces (GUIs) is required to enable data utilization even without in-depth programming knowledge

Data analysis: Analysis routines and scripts must be set up and described in such a way and described in such a way that others can easily apply them to their own data sets and can be customised under certain circumstances.” Rank equally high. The answers that were chosen least frequently (60%) were “Electronic lab books: MatWerk-specific software solutions are needed to document activities in the lab.” and “Basic infrastructure: From an infrastructure perspective, network access for devices must be generally be better guaranteed.”

The insights from this survey will allow us to verify our working program and development plans within NFDI-MatWerk.

A comparison to the past survey from 2020 will probably also indicate what advancements are already underway since then.

We will conduct another survey to follow up on the further advancements in the field.

This publication was written by the NFDI consortium NFDI-MatWerk in the context of the work of the association German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) e.V.. NFDI is financed by the Federal Republic of Germany and the 16 federal states and funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) – funding code M532701 / the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under the National Research Data Infrastructure – NFDI 38/1 – project number 460247524.